

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

WP1
SETTING LEGAL AND SOCIAL CONDITIONS
D1.3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT PLAN

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

APGA	Australian Pipelines and Gas Association Ltd
CA	Canary Islands
CIV	Civil society
EC	European Commission
ES	Spain
EU	European Union / European level
FR	France
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOBCAN ACIISI	- Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation, and Information Society
GOV	Government
IND	Industry
MU	multi-use
PC	Project Coordinator
PT	Portugal
QH	Quadruple Helix
TH	Triple Helix
UNI	University
W2Power	Wind to Power prototype

Executive summary

The aim of AquaWind is to perform a demonstration test of a multi-use (MU) integrated and co-located solution. This would consist of joining an existing marine renewable energy production Wind to Power (W2Power) prototype with an innovative finfish aquaculture solution. The aquaculture prototype will include a tailor-made design fish cage with novel net materials, high level of digitalization and species diversification. Whereas the W2Power will consist of floating wind technology. This project performs, for the first-time, MU test trials joining marine energy production with live fish aquaculture in the Atlantic region. AquaWind joins efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholders' consortia including R&D centres, companies, a regional authority, and a maritime cluster from three EU members states (FR, ES, PT) in the Atlantic basin. In addition to that, **AquaWind will involve a wide network of stakeholder throughout all the project phases to propitiate social acceptance.**

This document details, after a brief introduction, what the stakeholder engagement plan will be, through the type and degree of stakeholder participation and the channels of interaction, followed by stakeholder mapping and preparation for stakeholder engagement, through standard communication rules and GDPR compliance.

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Introduction

The Project

AquaWind is a European project that aims to perform a demonstration test of a MU technology solution joining marine renewable energy production and finfish aquaculture. The floating technology part consists of an already existing prototype developed by the project partner EnerOcean (the W2Power prototype), while the aquaculture solution entails a tailor-made design fish cage with novel net materials, high level of digitalization and species diversification. This project performs, for the first-time, MU test trials joining marine energy production with live fish aquaculture in the Atlantic region thanks to the efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholders' consortia including R&D centres, companies, a regional authority, and a maritime cluster from three EU members states (FR, ES, PT) in the Atlantic basin. In addition to that, AquaWind will involve a wide network of stakeholder throughout all the project phases to propitiate social acceptance, for which a Stakeholder Engagement Plan is needed.

The project will provide a route map for regulatory and legal issues that need to be addressed for real implementation of MU projects, taking advantages, and facilitating interaction with previous and ongoing EU funded projects. Additionally, AquaWind will demonstrate how the joint activity can be digitised to be remotely operated in the same maritime space with different fish species and how one activity might affect the other, before going one step further to becoming the new W2Power prototype in a commercial solution. Thus, AquaWind will provide real data to demonstrate the economic, environmental, and social sustainability of the MU proposal: providing a business model case and exploitation plan to evaluate the cost reduction of commissioning, maintenance and operation of the combined activity. Also, it will provide real data of the monitoring campaign to evaluate the environmental impact in surrounding maritime space following the CO2 footprint.

The Consortium

AquaWind consortium brings together a set of complementary and specialized partners located in the Atlantic area. The consortium is multi-actor and multidisciplinary and includes a regional authority, 5 companies and private research organizations, 1 university, and a cluster including companies and civil society organizations. In this way, the project ensures that knowledge and technology need as well as social acceptance and legal requirements are covered and build a comprehensive and inclusive framework for integrated planning and delivery of multiuse solutions in the Atlantic basin.

The consortium covers three Member States: France, Portugal, and Spain. Nonetheless, being **the solutions proposed located in Canary Islands the consortium counts with a majority of Spanish partners** which are needed for the installation of the prototype, management of legal requirements and social acceptance of local stakeholders. The Project Coordinator (PC) is the Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation, and Information Society (GOBCAN-ACIISI) which

is responsible for promoting scientific and technological research and development, business innovation in the Archipelago. GOBCAN-ACIISI will play a major role in ensuring institutional and social sustainability of AquaWind and its integration with regional research and innovation policies without increasing the impact on the territory or natural resources, and providing quality employment, all in line with the objectives set for the whole of the European Union (EU).

The consortium is listed below:

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Agencia Canaria De Investigación Innovación y Sociedad De La Información	GOBCAN-ACIISI	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC	ES
3.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT	ES
4	Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias	PLOCAN	ES
5	Asociación Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
6	EnerOcean S.L	EO	ES
7	INNOSEA	INNOSEA	FR
8	WAVEC/Offshore Renewables – Centro de Energía Offshore Associacao	WAVEC	PT
9	Canarias Explotaciones Marinas S.L	CANEXMAR	ES

Table 1. AquaWind 's consortium.

The Work Package 1

The WP1 aims at analysing the societal context for the development of AquaWind solutions, addressing in particular: administrative and legal challenges, addressing health and safety aspects and basis of social acceptance through stakeholder engagement.

Two tasks related to stakeholder engagement are included in WP1 and described below:

T1.3 Planning stakeholder engagement.

One of AquaWind's objectives is the implementation of an inclusive process, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritising public administrations, academia, business sector comprising the supply chain at local level, as well as social agents such as business associations, labour unions and NGOs with an environmental profile (youth, women, disabled, migrants). For this purpose, in collaboration with WP7 a mapping of stakeholders of the quadruple helix will be carried out previously to ensure a wide representation of these stakeholders as target groups in the communication and dissemination of the project. Then, in the first months of the

project, a technical survey will be launched to collect information from these stakeholders.

T1.4 Stakeholder engagement.

Based on the stakeholder engagement plan, and in conjunction with WP7, a set of diverse activities will be organized tailored to each type of organization, including interviews, focus groups, workshops, matchmaking activities. etc. This task will also include monitoring and reporting of the engagement activities. Specifically, once the plan is developed, a post-demonstration survey and a second participatory process will be carried out, therefore, stakeholder engagement will be established in two phases, one pre-demonstration and one post-demonstration with two surveys and at least two activities (interviews, focus groups, technical workshops, and/or matchmaking actions) in each round. This will serve to build a comprehensive and inclusive framework for an integrated planning and delivery of multiuse solutions in the Atlantic basin.

Further details on dissemination and communication activities aimed at successfully engaging stakeholders will be presented in paragraph 3.3.

To accomplish these tasks, the following deliverables will be carried out:

- Deliverable D1.3 – Stakeholder Engagement Plan. (It is this document).
- Deliverable D1.6 – D1.7 – D1.8 – D1.9 – D1.10 – Progress Report. 4 periodic reports will be produced, which will include the activities for the stakeholders' engagement in the AquaWind project, therefore there will be 4 versions of this document.

Communication and dissemination principles

Below is the set of five principles on which the AquaWind Dissemination and Communication Plan has been built (extracted from D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan):

- **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication and dissemination activities need to be adaptable to the project's various research themes and stakeholder communities and project progress. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.
- **Flexibility.** Communication needs to be flexible and open to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
- **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** AquaWind needs to be able to speak to a variety of actors and stakeholders with different background and objectives in mind. To achieve this, the project must formulate key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication using laymen's language).

- **Exploitation of synergies.** To maximize impact and efficiency of exploitation an extensive network of external collaborations of project partners will be used, and opportunities sought to join and contribute to existing networks and platforms which have relevant remits.
- **Gender sensitive and inclusive communication.** Certain words and images we use to communicate must be considered carefully since they can perpetuate images of socially prescribed gender roles and behaviours. AquaWind will adopt a non- hierarchical and nonpatronizing style, to promote gender-sensitive communication, identify gender stereotypes and use a fair and balanced representation of women and men in communication.

The quadruple helix approach (QH)

AquaWind will target representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model recognising four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society, being all four categories equally important for the project long-term success. Both the Triple Helix (TH) concept and the Quadruple Helix (QH) approach are grounded on the idea that innovation is the outcome of an interactive process involving different spheres of actors, each contributing according to its 'institutional' function in society. Traditional protagonists of the TH are University (UNI), Industry (IND), and Government (GOV). Civil society (CIV) is the additional sphere included in the QH. Contribution to innovation is envisaged in terms of sharing of knowledge and transfer of know-how, with the helix's models assigning and formalising a precise role to each sphere in supporting economic growth through innovation. As society becomes more and more interactive, the role of knowledge as well as the number and scope of spheres to be included in the innovation-generating process have been increasing over time.

The concept of QH was developed by maintaining the interaction of the spheres of the TH (UNI, IND, and GOV) and by formalising the role of civil society (e.g., Yawson, 2009). Academia and firms provide the necessary conditions for an integrated innovation ecosystem. Governments provide the regulatory framework and the financial support for the definition and implementation of innovation strategies and policies. Civil society not only uses and applies knowledge and demands for innovation in the form of goods and services, but also becomes an active part of the innovation system.

Stakeholder engagement is the process of involving those who have an interest in, or may be impacted by, infrastructure projects/options. Stakeholders include government agencies, infrastructure users and the local community.

Stakeholder engagement is a highly relevant activity, an ongoing process, that builds relationships between parties enabling information exchange. This process allows stakeholder affected by decisions of organisation in question to contribute to the decision-making process.

The general principles of stakeholder engagement policy planning are the following, which serve as an example for AquaWind:

- Engagement focuses on the best interests of the community.
- Engagement is open, honest, and meaningful.
- Approaches to engagement are inclusive and appropriate.
- Information is timely and relevant.
- Information is accurate, easy to understand and accessible.
- Decision-making is transparent.

The process of stakeholder engagement is voluntary, open, and active dialog, that identifies current position of all parties included, outlines objectives and outcomes, and identifies how to achieve them. Parties that are included in the engagement can change but the process of engagement is continues. The process of stakeholder engagement is multi-faceted process including (APGA Guideline for stakeholder engagement, 2015):

- Providing information.
- Capacity building to equip communities and stakeholders to effectively engage.
- Listening and responding to community and stakeholder concerns.
- Including communities and stakeholders in relevant decision-making processes.
- Developing goodwill and an understanding of objectives and priorities which will lead to confidence in decisions.
- Establishing a realistic understanding of potential outcomes; and
- Building an understanding of the decision-making process.

For stakeholder engagement to be effective there are some requirements, which will be also considered for the AquaWind project: willingness and motivation of stakeholders to participate (Gunton et al., 2010); inclusivity of all possible interests (Reed, 2008); equal access to information and knowledge (Gunton et al., 2010; Gopnik et al., 2017).

The main value of engagement with stakeholders lies in understanding of dialogue dynamics and enabled participation (Luoma-Aho, 2015). Generally, engagement is referred as interaction between stakeholders and organisation where interaction influences stakeholder thoughts, actions, and emotions toward organisation (Broodie et al., 2011). Although some challenges might emerge in the management of such stakeholder relationships and not all stakeholders might be interested in participating in knowledge creation, the benefits of the QH stakeholder approach by development of collaborative network are, in conclusion, evident through access to knowledge, development of scientific competence, obtaining competitive advantage through acceleration of ideas.

1. Stakeholder Engagement Plan

1.1 Type and Degree of Stakeholder Engagement

One of AquaWind's objectives is the implementation of an inclusive process, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritizing public administrations, academia, business sector comprising the supply chain at local level, as well as social agents such as business associations, fishermen and civil society.

Stakeholders will be, first of all, approached mainly through public surveys and in some cases through sector-specific surveys (as is the case for the artisanal fisheries sector, among others). These surveys will be made available to stakeholders through an online form that will be made available to stakeholders in two rounds of consultation (one prior to the installation of the device at sea and one once the device is back on land). It has been decided to do this because, according to consultations carried out mainly on offshore wind devices, the visual and environmental impact is usually the one that raises the most doubts, even though these devices have very rigorous environmental impact assessments.

To complement survey feedback, throughout the project, dissemination actions are foreseen, mainly included in WP7, during which the stakeholder engagement plan will be applied through interviews, focus groups, technical workshops, and matchmaking actions. Depending on the actions included in WP7 the approach will be at different levels:

- **Informative participation (knowledge diffusion):** according to the actions included in WP7.
- **Consultative participation (knowledge utilization):** this will be the main way of approaching stakeholders. Apart from the possibilities of carrying out public surveys online, we will also take advantage of events in which AquaWind partners participate and have a role as organizer or collaborator to distribute the surveys to sectors of interest.
- **Collaborative participation (where the stakeholders will be directly involved in co-creation of knowledge):** according to the actions included in WP7 and the WPs (e.g., WP2, WP3, WP4) on technical development of the energy generating device and fish farming.

An effective project stakeholder management is required to coordinate interactions between the consortium partners for involvement of the stakeholders in different tasks (Pernille E. & Lund Jepsen A., 2016).

1.2 Engagement Channels

In the proposal phase, the project team has identified a series of engagement channels, through actions included in WP7, that include physical meetings and digital tools which will facilitate stakeholder participation in consultation and mutual learning process.

1.2.1 Online consultations via surveys

For the online consultation actions or through the distribution of surveys in specific events, that are carried out in the project or in others in which AquaWind partners are involved, during the first months of the project, bibliographic research has been carried out related to the elaboration of social perception surveys mainly related to offshore wind energy. Through this analysis, partners have identified a wide range of questions that will be included in the different phases of the consultation. The survey template has been finalised in local language (Spanish) given that the aim is to facilitate it to local communities in the Canary Islands (the pilot demonstration site), who might not speak English.

The sources of information used for the development of the survey have been:

Sources of information

Asociación Empresarial Eólica (AEE), (2021). Preguntas frecuentes sobre la eólica marina en España.

<https://www.aeeolica.org/images/Posicionamientos/FQ-EOLICA-MARINA-PDF-def.pdf>

Arbeitsgemeinschaft Offshore-Windenergie e.V., (2017). Repräsentative Umfrage zu Offshore-Windenergie im Auftrag der AGOW.

<https://bwo-offshorewind.de/repraesentative-umfrage-zum-ausbau-von-windenergie-auf-see/>

Cabinet Secretary for Net Zero, Energy and Transport. (2022). Offshore wind farm developments – public perceptions: survey.

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/public-perceptions-offshore-wind-farm-developments-scotland/pages/9/>

Ipsos Iberia S.A. para Vientos de Futuro – Asociación Empresarial Eólica – AEE. (2022). La percepción social de la energía eólica en España – Resultados principales.

https://vientosdefuturo.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Estudio-de-percepcion_Vientos-de-futuro.pdf

Buck, J., (2019). Indicators of social acceptance of offshore wind energy development in Massachusetts: assessing the commonwealth's current socio- political, market and community conditions. University of Rhode Island.

<https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2715&context=theses>

Sources of information

Cronin, Y., Cummins, V., Wolsztynski, E. (2019). Public perception of offshore wind farms in Ireland. University College Cork, Ireland.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308597X21004255>

Devine-Wright, P; Wiersma, B. (2019). Understanding community acceptance of a potential offshore wind energy project in different locations: An island- based analysis of 'place- technology fit'. University of Exeter.

<https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10871/40508/EP%20Revision%202%20updated%20references.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y>

Geraint, E., Gianluca, F., (2016). The social acceptance of wind energy. European Commission.

https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC103743/jrc103743_2016.7095_src_en_social%20acceptance%20of%20wind_am%20-%20qf%20final.pdf

Hattam, C., Hooper, T., Beaumont, N. (2015). Public Perceptions of Offshore Wind Farms. The Crown State.

https://www.offshorewindindustry.com/sites/default/files/public_perceptions_the_crown_estate.pdf

Kim, H.J., Kim, J.H., Yoo, S.H., (2019). Social acceptance of offshore wind energy development in South Korea: Results from a choice experiment survey. Department of Energy Policy, Graduate School of Energy & Environment, Seoul National University of Science & Technology, Republic of Korea.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1364032119304538?via%3Dihub>

Nielsen, L, (2009). Social acceptance of wind energy projects "winning Hearts and Minds". Country report of Denmark. The International Energy Agency Implementing Agreement for Co-operation in the Research, Development, and Deployment of Wind Energy Systems.

http://www.socialacceptance.ch/images/state-of-the-art_acceptance_wind_energy_denmark.pdf

Tudela, M., y Molina, J. (2006). La percepción social de las energías renovables a través de una encuesta de opinión. Un caso práctico en localidades del noroeste murciano. Universidad de Murcia.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/26495810_La_percepcion_social_de_las_energias_renovables_a_traves_de_una_encuesta_de_opinion_un_caso_practico_en_localidades_del_noroeste_murciano/link/0a85e52e761d8bd842000000/download

Wiersma, B., (2015). Public acceptability of offshore wind and tidal energy Guernsey. University of Exeter.

<https://www.gov.gg/CHttpHandler.ashx?id=148289&p=0>

Offshorewindenergy.org

Sources of information

https://www.offshorewindenergy.org/CA-OWEE/Env_4.html

Table 2. Sources of information for the elaboration of the surveys.

1.2.2 Other channels and tools

Beyond the surveys envisaged in WP1, the project aims to promote a wide range of dissemination and communication activities under WP7 closely related to WP1 stakeholder engagement objectives and outcomes. As defined in the D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, dedicated channels have been foreseen for each type of QH stakeholder groups, along with the type of information and key messages to be shared. The table below provides an overview of the AquaWind planning for stakeholders' reach-out:

Target group	Communication channels	Type of information
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results 	
Industry Representatives, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business/exploitation plan 	
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project impact assessment 	
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantages of the prototype 	

Table 3. Target groups communication details.

2. Mapping Stakeholders

Mapping is an important step in understanding who the key stakeholders are, which expertise they have, and where and how they can contribute to the project. The objective of a mapping exercise is to ensure that potential external experts who might have an interest or a stake in the project's results have been identified. This will lead to a more efficient and targeted communication strategy and will ensure high quality contributions from the stakeholders.

2.1 Identification of Stakeholders

The AquaWind project has a special characteristic: even though it involves three different countries (ES, PT and FR), the actions will be carried out mainly in Spain and specifically in the Canary Islands, so the mapping of actors will have a strong regional character. However, given that AquaWind's main objective is to carry out a demonstration test of an integrated and co-located multi-use (MU) solution between two devices, one for wind energy generation and the other for fish farming, stakeholders related to these two sectors at national and European level, with the countries participating in the project and at European level, will be considered.

The identification of stakeholders has been done based on the experience of the project partners and considering the actors of the quadruple helix. The following table includes those stakeholders according to whether they are regional (Canary Islands - CA), national (ES, PT, FR) or European (EU) and clustered according to:

- Research community (researchers, PhD students)
- Industry Representatives, Investors
- Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)
- Policy and decision-makers
- Fisheries communities

A description of the targeted stakeholder groups of AquaWind is provided below.

Stakeholder groups	Description
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	Science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to marine activities. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and Phd scientists. The science category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Industry Representatives, Investors	This category includes representatives of the fishery sector, aquaculture, renewable energy but also maritime transport. In particular companies willing to commercialise the products and services developed in the demo work packages will require robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, which will be produced under WP5. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities and communication activities offered under WP7.

Stakeholder groups	Description
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)	This category includes both citizens and organizations which operate in the marine field and are affected by marine related activities and citizens who have no specific knowledge of MUP and are not affected by marine activities in their everyday life. The general public will receive awareness-raising materials to trigger their interest, improve their literacy on renewable energy and aquaculture needs and their relevance for climate change mitigation and food production. In addressing the public, citizen science activities will be promoted as for the first group, environmental organizations, local action groups, and other type of associations will be reached to provide them with comprehensive information on AquaWind solutions and to foster social acceptance.
Policy and decision-makers	They will require short and concise recommendations and visual documentation facilitating the understanding of how MUP can impact a broader policy sector and how policy can support or hamper the installations of MUPs. Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted. At EU level several Directorates-General will be reached (RTD, CLIMA, ENER, ENV, MARE), the JRC, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency; the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group.
Fisheries communities	The approach to the fishing community will be carried out through the Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs). FLAGs are entities with their own local development strategies, which in specific fishing and aquaculture areas bring together companies, public entities, third sector and research entities to implement the strategies.

Table 4. Stakeholder groups description.

Based on the stakeholder groups identified, a comprehensive mapping has been performed to identify the main organisations and representatives which should be targeted by the project's dissemination and engagement actions.

Stakeholder groups	Name of the stakeholder
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (CA) Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria – ULPGC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Instituto Universitario de Acuicultura Sostenible y Ecosistemas Marinos (IU-ECOQUA) ○ Instituto Universitario de Oceanografía y Cambio Global (IOGAG) ○ Instituto Universitario de Turismo y Desarrollo Económico Sostenible (TIDES)

Stakeholder groups	Name of the stakeholder
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Estudios Ambientales y Recursos Naturales (i-UNAT) ○ Instituto Universitario de Sanidad Animal y Seguridad Alimentaria (IUSA) ○ Instituto Universitario de Sistemas Inteligentes y Aplicaciones Numéricas en Ingeniería (SIANI) ○ Instituto Universitario de Ciencias y Tecnologías Cibernéticas (IUCTC) ○ Instituto Universitario para el Desarrollo Tecnológico y la Innovación en Comunicaciones (IDeTIC) ○ Instituto Universitario de Microelectrónica Aplicada (IUMA) ○ Group for the Research on Renewable Energy Systems (GRRES) ○ Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (FPCT-UPGC) ○ Banco Español de Algas (BEA) (CA) Fundación Universitaria de Las Palmas – FULP
<p>Industry Representatives, Investors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (EU) Inversores – all the utilities (e.g Equinor, Iberdrola, Plenitude, ENEL, OceanWinds etc..)

Stakeholder groups	Name of the stakeholder
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (CA) ECOLOGISTAS EN ACCIÓN – BEN MAGEC
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (ORs) Comité de Suivi of the EU Outermost Regions
Fisheries communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (CA) Asociación de armadores y pescadores de Canarias (MIRACANARIAS)

² Consejería de derechos sociales, igualdad, diversidad y juventud. Listado de entidades acreditadas para el voluntariado. <https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/derechossociales/voluntariado/registro/index.html>

Stakeholder groups	Name of the stakeholder
	(CA) Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural de la isla de La Palma (GAC La Palma)
	(CA) Asociación Insular de Desarrollo Rural de La Gomera (AIDER La Gomera)
	(CA) Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural y Pesquero de Lanzarote (ADERLAN Lanzarote)
	(CA) Asociación Grupo de Acción Social y Pesquera El Hierro (GALP El Hierro)
	(EU) Consejo Consultivo de las Regiones Ultraperiféricas (CC RUP)

Table 5. Identified stakeholders.

3. Engagement of stakeholders

3.1 Overall approach to stakeholder engagement

A centralised stakeholder engagement will ensure that the stakeholders are involved in a focused and efficient way with mutual benefits. Furthermore, it will ensure that the project is adhering to appropriate rules for privacy policy and ethics in personal data management.

As mentioned in previous sections, the relationship with stakeholders will be mainly linked to WP1 consultation through anonymous surveys, in which no personal data is collected. In these surveys, the person is invited to connect with AquaWind's media channels like the website, follow social media accounts, and subscribe to the newsletter to be regularly informed of AquaWind's actions. Relevant stakeholders can also contact the AquaWind consortium through the general project email activated for contacts with the external public.

Beyond the WP1 consultations, additional stakeholder engagement activities are foreseen under WP7 as part of the dissemination and communication roadmap of the project. AquaWind will promote events, conferences, webinars, technical meetings, interviews, etc targeting and involving a wide range of stakeholders.

3.2 Standardised rules for contacting stakeholders

Stakeholders and, overall, the general public will be reached by digital communication and dissemination activities as planned in WP7 e.g., through website's promotion, social media posts and campaigns, publication of releases on local press, promotion of newsletters, sharing of project promotional videos, sharing of promotional materials, etc. Stakeholders will be able to subscribe to the project newsletter in a dedicated form published on the AquaWind website and will be receiving periodic newsletters from the project. They will be able to unsubscribe at any time if they wanted, in line with the project Data Management Plan and GDPR rules.

As part of stakeholder engagement activities, the consortium might also promote the project on open-access stakeholder platforms or working groups, as well as contacts publicly available on institutional websites.

In the specific case of organisation of project events, webinars, and conferences, the activities with stakeholders will be promoted by all consortium partners among their channels to maximise reach-out. For events, an official invitation letter, an agenda, and a registration form will be shared to allow people sign up to project activities. Only necessary personal data will be asked in the registration process i.e., name, surname, and email contact to allow the responsible partner to manage the logistic and organisational aspects of the events.

A short and clear Informed Consent Form will be included in the registration process to express consent in participating in the activity and allowing the use of personal data for organisational purposes. Moreover, an optional specific consent will be included to ask interested participants

if they consent to be included in the newsletter subscribers and re-contacted for future events organised by the project.

3.3 Communication and dissemination activity

The effect and impact of AquaWind will rely greatly on effective communication. AquaWind needs to engage with a different set of actors such as the once described previously. WP7 will lead the project's communication and dissemination efforts in close synergy with WP5 which will foster and maximize the exploitation opportunities of the AquaWind multi-use solution.

Communication and dissemination activities in AquaWind will aim thus at ensuring visibility of the project but also at triggering effective interactions with stakeholders at the many project's interfaces.

As set in the Grant Agreement, different communication messages will be delivered to the above-mentioned audiences through a set of communication tools:

- Videos, infographics, and other visual documentation of AquaWind and MUP activities, achievement, and impact will be produced. These tools will help to raise public awareness on the potential of multi-use platforms, renewable energy production, etc., while explaining the importance of the EU support to this type of initiative, and specifically of EMFAF. They will also be shared on the project social media accounts, on the AquaWind's webpage and used when relevant during seminars, trainings and workshops;
- Dedicated events including the final conference will be organised by the project;
- Presentations and networking at relevant local, regional, and national events; b2b meetings can be also organised for a focused engagement and feedback with specific target groups such as policy makers, industry and civil society. Presentations at schools on multi-use solutions will be also considered to raise awareness of children and their families general public;
- Dedicated webinars will be organised to reach mainly scientists and innovators on one side and policy makers on the other side. Webinars with policy makers will aim mainly at enabling a favourable legislative and administrative context for the deployment of MUP solutions in the Atlantic area and to provide policy makers with figures and estimations on the impact of MUP in different policy areas (environment, marine planning, employment, etc). The format of the webinar will be designed according to the target group. The webinars will be organised in advance including the participation of outstanding speakers and foreseeing space for discussion;
- Seminars and/or trainings will be organised to build the consortium and external organisations' skills on concepts and operations at the MU installations. These events will be mainly focused on the prototype operation and maintenance and on the remote management tools, to emphasise and share the innovative outcomes of the project.

4. Review and improvement

Once a stakeholder engagement activity is completed, it is essential to document, review and assess the engagement process, as well as the input and the feedback received from the stakeholders. With this, the project team will be able to measure the effectiveness of the engagement activity and if needed define further action items, revisit original plans, revise the project goals, and adopt the future steps.

For an effective evaluation of an engagement activity, the number and relevance of stakeholders and the quantity of their inputs and feedback, are among the key evaluation criteria. However, by conducting a targeted survey with well-thought questions, more in-depth analysis of the engagement activity can be performed.

This assessment will be included as part of the progress report to be drafted in month 6, 12, 24 and 30.

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Annexes

SURVEY TEMPLATE (Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25th October 2022 in Gran Canaria)

AquaWind is a groundbreaking project in the Atlantic region, which aims through a practical and disruptive demonstration of integrated solutions for the development of offshore renewable energy to design and implement a demonstration test. This will involve pairing a W2Power prototype for marine renewable energy production with an innovative fish aquaculture solution, including a custom-designed fish cage with novel netting materials, high digitalization level and species diversification.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to obtain statistical data which will be included in the project reports and no personal data will be requested.

SEX:

- Male
 Female

Age:

- Less than 25
 Between 25- 50
 More than 50

Occupational sector:

- Primary sector
 Student
 Service sector
 Construction
 Household
 Unemployed
 Retiree
 Industrial sector
 Other: _____

Resident of the Canary Islands:

- YES
 NO

What are your views on renewable energy?

- In favor
 Against

Do you know the different types of renewable energy that exist?

- YES
 NO

What type of renewable energy do you think is the most suitable?

- Photovoltaic energy
 Wind energy
 Hydraulic energy
 Tidal energy
 Geothermal energy
 Biomass energy

What do you think about offshore renewable energies?

- Beneficial
 Detrimental

 Do you agree with the installation of offshore wind farms in the selected areas?

- YES
 NO

 What do you think is the main drawback to the implementation of offshore wind farms?

- Visual impact
 Environmental impact
 Proximity
 Number of turbines required

 Would you support the installation of other types of renewable energy in the coastal zone and/or at sea?

- YES
 NO

 Do you know of any renewable energy companies?

- YES
 NO

 Do you believe that offshore wind energy is widely supported by society?

- YES
 NO

 Do you believe that you have the required information at hand regarding the marine renewable energy projects that are being planned in the Canary Islands?

- YES
 NO

 Are you acquainted with the relevant legislation on the implementation and development of offshore energy?

- YES
 NO

 Do you think that the implementation of this type of renewable energy on your island will contribute to the island's economic growth?

- YES
 NO

 Do you think that installing this type of energy is an advantage for your island?

- YES
 NO

 If yes, please select the one that you consider to be the major advantage:

- Economic
 Unlimited resource
 Benefits to the citizens
 Other: _____

 Do you think that this type of renewable energy will contribute significantly towards reducing dependency on fossil fuel imports and thus CO2 generation?

- YES
 NO

 In your opinion, should we use renewable energy and rely less on the other energies, such as burning fossil fuels?

- YES
 NO

 Do you know the "Roadmap for the development of offshore wind and marine energy in Spain"?

- YES
 NO

 Are you aware of the objectives of the Roadmap for the Canary Islands, as a "launching pad" for the implementation of this type of renewable energy in our islands?

- YES
 NO

 Are you aware of the EU Clean Energy for EU Islands initiative, which aims to accelerate the transition to clean energy on all EU islands?

- YES
- NO

 Are you familiar with the National Integrated Energy and Climate plan 2021-2030?

- YES
- NO

 Have you heard about the Canary Islands Marine Renewable Energy strategy developed in 2021?

- YES
- NO

 Do you think offshore wind energy is a competitive advantage when it comes to the ORs (Outermost Regions of the European Union)?

- YES
- NO

 Regarding the information available on the installation of this prototype on the PLOCAN test bed, do you think it is inadequate?

- YES
- NO

 As for the small-scale fishing sector, do you think that the implementation of offshore wind energy jeopardizes its activity?

- YES
- NO

 In your opinion, does the implementation of this type of prototype, which combines energy generation and aquaculture, represent an advantage for the development of both sectors?

- YES
- NO

 With reference to the previous question, do you think that such implementation can improve the competitiveness of the aquaculture sector?

- YES
- NO

 Are you aware of the way in which services such as monitoring, testing and maintenance are provided to these multipurpose platforms?

- YES
- NO

 Do you think that the small-scale fishing sector can contribute to the above-described activities?

- YES
- NO

 If you could help in the implementation of such activities, would you agree to carry them out?

- YES
- NO

 Would you like to get in touch with...?

- Receive information.
- Participate in activities.
- Both: receive information and participate
- I do not wish to be contacted.

 If you would like to be contacted, how would you like to be reached?

- Website / social media
- Newsletter / Newsletter to your email
- By phone
- WhatsApp / SMS
- Other: _____

 Would you like to participate in activities/events organized in the Project such as courses, trainings, conferences, participatory meetings, interviews, surveys, etc?

- Yes
- No

 If you are interested in participating, please select the activities in which you would be willing to participate:

- Webinar / Web seminar
- Informative face-to-face meeting
- Round table
- Training
- Surveys
- Interviews
- Other: _____

 If so, you can contact AQUAWIND's partners using the following contact details:

Email: info@aquawind.eu

Telephone: (+34) 828041258

We would also like to provide you with our social networks in case you wish to be updated on the results of the Project or where you can contact us:

Instagram: @aquawind_

Facebook: AquaWind Project

LinkedIn: AquaWind Project

Twitter: AquaWind Project

 Remarks (include here any comments or observation you may have):

SURVEY TEMPLATE (XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AQUAWIND was presented on 23rd November 2022)

AquaWind is a groundbreaking project in the Atlantic region, which aims through a practical and disruptive demonstration of integrated solutions for the development of offshore renewable energy to design and implement a demonstration test. This will involve pairing a W2Power prototype for marine renewable energy production with an innovative fish aquaculture solution, including a custom-designed fish cage with novel netting materials, high digitalization level and species diversification.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to obtain statistical data which will be included in the project reports and no personal data will be requested.

SEX:

- Male
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Age:

- Less than 25
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 Against

Do you know the different types of renewable energy that exist?

- YES
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What type of renewable energy do you think is the most suitable?

- Photovoltaic energy
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 Tidal energy
 Geothermal energy
 Biomass energy

What do you think about offshore renewable energies?

- Beneficial
 Detrimental

 Do you agree with the installation of offshore wind farms in the selected areas?

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 What do you think is the main drawback to the implementation of offshore wind farms?

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 Environmental impact
 Proximity
 Number of turbines required

 Would you support the installation of other type of renewable energy in the coastal zone and/or at sea?

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 NO

 Do you know of any renewable energy companies?

- YES
 NO

 Do you believe that offshore wind energy is widely supported by society?

- YES
 NO

 Do you believe that you have the required information at hand regarding the marine renewable energy projects that are being planned in your community?

- YES
 NO

 Are you acquainted with the relevant legislation on the implementation and development of offshore energy?

- YES
 NO

 Do you think that the implementation of this type of renewable energy on your island will contribute to the island's economic growth?

- YES
 NO

 Do you think that installing this type of energy is an advantage for your community?

- YES
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 If yes, please select the one that you consider to be the major advantage:

- Economic
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 Other: _____

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- YES
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 In your opinion, should we use renewable energy and rely less on the other energies, such as burning fossil fuels?

- YES
 NO

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- YES
 NO

 Are you aware of the EU Clean Energy for EU Islands initiative, which aims to accelerate

 Are you familiar with the National Integrated Energy and Climate plan 2021-2030?

- YES

the transition to clean energy on all EU islands?

NO

YES

NO

 Have you heard about the Canary Islands Marine Renewable Energy strategy developed in 2021?

YES

NO

 In your opinion, does the implementation of this type of prototype, which combines energy generation and aquaculture, represent an advantage for the development of both sectors?

YES

NO

 Do you think offshore wind energy is a competitive advantage when it comes to the ORs (Outermost Regions of the European Union)?

YES

NO

 As for the aquaculture sector, do you think that the implementation of offshore wind energy jeopardizes its activity?

YES

 NO

 With reference to the previous question, do you think that such implementation can improve the competitiveness of the aquaculture sector?

YES

NO

 Are you aware of the way in which services such as monitoring, testing and maintenance are provided to these multipurpose platforms?

YES

NO

 Do you think that the aquaculture sector can contribute to the above-described activities?

YES

NO

 If you could help in the implementation of such activities, would you agree to carry them out?

YES

NO

 Would you like to get in touch with ...?

Receive information.

Participate in activities.

Both: receive information and participate

I do not wish to be contacted.

 If you would like to be contacted, how would you like to be reached?

Website / social media

Newsletter / Newsletter to your email

By phone

WhatsApp / SMS

Other: _____

 Would you like to participate in activities/events organized in the Project such as courses, trainings, conferences,

 If so, you can contact AQUAWIND's partners using the following contact details:

participatory meetings, interviews, surveys...?

- Yes
- No

 If you are interested in participating, please select the activities in which you would be willing to participate:

- Webinar / Web seminar
- Informative face-to-face meeting
- Round table
- Training
- Surveys
- Interviews
- Other: _____

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Instagram: @aquawind_

Facebook: AquaWind Project

LinkedIn: AquaWind Project

Twitter: AquaWind Project

 Remarks (include here any comments or observation you may have):

This survey version can also be accessed online at the link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeFnESDGoYr5WUIU49UOwnoRw0UjLMW6E919XkvAPkYJHfEjGw/viewform>

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

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